

Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the map of research developments regarding Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 2013 to 2022 by searching the national journal indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Zakah Management". Based on the search results, there were 60 research articles, which were then input into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a Library Research study. The research results show that the number of publications has increased significantly every year. And based on the mapping results using the VOSviewer application, research regarding Zakah Management is divided into 11 clusters and 133 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of the Library Research study, there are 3 main themes surrounding Mobile Banking in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Zakah Management; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Institutions

1. Introduction

The role of management in companies, especially in Islamic Financial Institutions, is very important. This is in accordance with the understanding of management as a process that includes planning, organizing, directing and supervising all efforts within the organization including the use of organizational resources to achieve the desired goals. Meanwhile, Zakah means increasing or developing if translated literally, Zakah is defined as a form of worship to Allah by setting aside a portion of assets based on the levels determined by Islamic law. Zakah must be given to groups determined by the Shari'a and is an obligation for every person who is Muslim.

In previous research, Zakah management can be translated as a Zakah management system which includes several activities such as planning, implementation and coordination in collecting, distributing and utilizing Zakah. Zakah management is very important in increasing the effectiveness of Zakah management in Islamic Financial Institutions. On the other hand, good Zakah management can increase sharia-based economic development, especially in several financial institutions and banks in Indonesia. In his research entitled "Modernization of Zakah Management in Lazismu " to specifically interpret Zakah management in Lazismu on a modern basis. This research was conducted with reference to aspects of modernization in management. Furthermore, in his research, the management of Lazismu is reviewed from three sides, namely management, origin of assets, payments, and distribution methods which are carried out thoroughly by implementing a modernization system in ZIS management. However, in the context of the origin of assets and payments, some still apply the traditional system. The potential for Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions is very large, considering the large number of customers who use Islamic Financial products and services. Islamic Financial Institutions can utilize the potential of Zakah to increase economic empowerment and social welfare for mustahik, such as productive economic empowerment programs, educational scholarships and health assistance. By properly utilizing Zakah, Islamic Financial Institutions can strengthen their

position as financial institutions that care about the social and economic welfare of Muslims.

Scientific publications about Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions are still relatively few if seen on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Based on data searches, there are 101 studies on Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions, especially in banks or sharia banking. Therefore, researchers want to conduct research on Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions in Indonesia, considering that Islamic Financial Institutions continue to develop rapidly in both banks and non-banks as time goes by. This research has differences with several previous studies. The discussion in this research focuses on mapping research on Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions which has never been discussed by other researchers. The aim is to find out the extent of research development in Islamic Financial Institutions regarding Zakah Management from 2013 to 2022. This research was conducted using bibliometric methods, VOSviewer software and Library Research studies.

2. Library Research

Zakah management is a pattern of Zakah management with clear objectives and an achievement process that uses human resources or the help of modern technology. Zakah management is applied to structure the management of Zakah funds effectively and efficiently, in accordance with the definition of management, namely a process that includes planning, organizing, mobilizing and controlling to achieve the expected goals.

Bibliometric studies are a branch of science that analyzes and evaluates scientific publications and related information. It involves the use of statistical and informatics methodologies to assess the production, citation, and dissemination of knowledge in scientific literature. Bibliometric studies can be used to measure the performance and contributions of individuals, institutions and scientific fields, as well as to understand interactions and relationships between scientific fields and publications. It can also help in the identification and evaluation of trends and issues in the scientific literature.

VOSviewer is a useful software for organizing, browsing, and depicting network meta data. VOSviewer is widely used in research to analyze bibliometrics, search for cases that have not been widely studied, and search for references that are frequently used in certain fields and other fields.

Library Research is the process of observing or researching literature from various sources, articles, journals and other publications according to the research topic being conducted. The aim of the Library Research is to make the stages of reviewing each source more structured and systematic in its implementation.

3. Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in Library Research studies. The object of the research is Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Zakah on Sharia Banks/Banking " for the entire year period (20-13-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable

Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research studies (Budianto, 2022) .

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Mapping of Scientific Publications Regarding Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions

The results of searching scientific publications regarding Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions over a period of 10 years, namely from 2013 to 2022, show an increase in publications every year, especially in the last 4 years. Publication data was obtained in the form of articles totaling 60 titles originating from accredited national journals. The most publications occurred in 2021 and 2022, namely the publication reached 10 articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Zakah Management by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2013	1	2017	7	2020	8
2014	3	2018	5	2021	10
2015	2	2019	9	2022	10
2016	5				
Total 60					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

In table 2, it is known that there are 3 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles regarding Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. The institution that publishes the most related research results is an economics journal, with 11 articles.

Table 2. Journals that publish scientific publications about Zakah Management

Name of Institution/Affiliation	Number of Publications
Journal of Accounting and Management Research	2
Masharif Al - Syariah Journal	3
Economic Journal	11

Source: Data processed, Microsoft Excel 201 6.

Table 3 shows that out of a total of 60 published research articles regarding Zakah management on the website Garuda, the most productive researcher is Rika Febri Ramdhani (Tadulako University, Palu) who wrote 2 journal articles. Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote 1 journal article.

4.2 Bibliometric mapping of research regarding Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions

The results of withdrawing research articles via the GARUDA (Digital Reference Guard) website are sent in the form of a Research Information System (RIS), entered and described using VOS Viewer. The results are as follows:

bank, Islamic corporate government, Islamic income ratio, Islamic investment ratio, multiple linear regression, profit sharing ratio, sharia compliance.

- Cluster 9, light purple consists of 8 topics, namely: accord, allocation, concept, corporate social response, fund, obligation, social responsibility, Zakah fund.
- Cluster 10, pink consists of 6 topics, namely: company ggbs, iscr, Islamic corporate social, performance, reputation.
- Cluster 11, light green color consists of 4 topics, namely: bank interest, Islamic law, law, usury.

4.3 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions

First, distribution/distribution of Zakah. Islamic Financial institutions (LKS) play an important role in the distribution of Zakah in the Muslim community. They facilitate the collection and distribution of Zakah by ensuring that Zakah funds are used for purposes permitted in Islamic teachings. The following are several ways how LKS distributes Zakah: (1) LKS can offer a Zakah program that allows donors to give their Zakah directly to people in need. LKS can verify prospective Zakah recipients to ensure that they meet the requirements to receive Zakah. (2) LKS can collaborate with Zakah amil institutions that have been approved by the government. This Zakah amil institution is responsible for collecting and distributing Zakah to eligible recipients. (3) LKS can establish partnerships with organizations or institutions that have a similar mission to distribute Zakah to people in need. This partnership program can help increase effectiveness and efficiency in Zakah distribution. (4) LKS can invest the Zakah funds received into social projects aimed at helping people in need. For example, LKS can build health or education infrastructure that will benefit society.

Second, management of Zakah funds. Islamic Financial institutions have an important role in managing Zakah funds because they are responsible for collecting, storing and distributing Zakah funds from people who wish to pay Zakah. The following are general steps in managing Zakah funds at Islamic Financial institutions: (1) Islamic Financial institutions must have a transparent and accountable Zakah collection system. They must collect Zakah funds from the community and store them in a special account that is separated from other accounts. (2) The Zakah funds collected must be kept in a special account that is separated from other accounts and managed separately from other funds. This aims to ensure that Zakah funds are not mixed with other funds and can be managed properly. (3) Islamic Financial institutions must have an effective and efficient Zakah distribution system. Zakah funds must be distributed to Zakah recipients who meet the requirements in accordance with the provisions of the Islamic religion. This must be done transparently and accountably so that it can be held accountable. (4) Islamic Financial institutions must carry out regular reporting regarding the collection, storage and distribution of Zakah. This report must be submitted to the Zakah supervisory institution and the community in order to ensure that Zakah funds have been managed well and on target. (5) Islamic Financial institutions must carry out regular Zakah audits by independent audit institutions that understand sharia principles. This aims to ensure that Zakah funds are managed well and in accordance with sharia principles.

Third, the social responsibility of Zakah. Islamic Financial institutions have social responsibility in managing Zakah received from customers or the public. Some of the social responsibilities of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions include: (1) Providing Zakah services that are easily accessible and transparent for the community. Islamic Financial institutions must ensure that customers or the public

can access Zakah services easily and transparently, so that the Zakah funds collected can be used effectively to help people in need. (2) Manage Zakah funds professionally and responsibly. Islamic Financial institutions must ensure that the Zakah funds collected are managed professionally and responsibly, in accordance with applicable sharia principles. (3) Helping people in need through social programs. Islamic Financial institutions must use the Zakah funds collected to help communities in need, such as scholarship programs, community economic development, and humanitarian aid. (4) Building social awareness and education about Zakah. Islamic Financial institutions must help increase social awareness and education about Zakah, so that people can understand the importance of paying Zakah and how Zakah can be used to help people in need.

Fourth, allocation of Zakah funds. The following are several steps that Islamic Financial institutions can take to allocate Zakah funds: (1) Forming a Zakah committee which is responsible for managing Zakah funds and determining Zakah recipients. This committee must consist of people who are experts in sharia law and have sufficient experience in dealing with Zakah. (2) Collecting Zakah funds from the community. Islamic Financial institutions must ensure that the Zakah funds collected come from halal sources and comply with Islamic sharia principles. (3) Determining Zakah recipients who are entitled to receive Zakah. Zakah recipients must meet the criteria set by Islamic sharia law, such as people who are indigent, poor, in debt, and so on. (4) Distribute Zakah funds to Zakah recipients in a halal manner and in accordance with Islamic sharia principles. For example, Zakah funds can be distributed in the form of cash assistance, goods assistance, or by providing business capital to Zakah recipients. (5) Monitoring and evaluating the use of Zakah funds that have been distributed to Zakah recipients. Islamic Financial institutions must ensure that the Zakah funds are used appropriately and in accordance with the stated objectives.

Fifth, the Maqashid sharia approach to Zakah funds. The following are several things that need to be considered in the Maqashid Syariah approach in managing Zakah funds in Islamic Financial institutions: (1) Zakah recipients must meet established sharia criteria, such as the poor, the poor, Zakah amil, and so on. Islamic Financial institutions must ensure that the selected Zakah recipients are those who really need it and meet the sharia criteria. (2) Islamic Financial institutions must ensure that the Zakah funds managed are only used for purposes that are truly needed by Zakah recipients, such as meeting basic needs, health, education, and so on. (3) Islamic Financial institutions must manage Zakah funds in a transparent and accountable manner, by providing clear and easy to understand information about the management of Zakah funds to interested parties. (4) Islamic Financial institutions must encourage Zakah recipients to be independent and develop, by providing assistance that is not only consumptive, but also productive. For example, by providing business capital assistance or skills training.

Sixth, payment of Zakah. The following are the steps for paying Zakah through financial institutions in Indonesia: (1) Select the Islamic Financial institution you want to use to pay Zakah. Make sure the institution is registered and recognized by the National Zakah Amil Agency (BAZNAS) or other Zakah institutions. (2) Make an appointment with the Zakah officer at the selected financial institution. Before making a payment, the officer will usually provide consultation and explanation on how to calculate and pay Zakah. (3) After calculating the amount of Zakah that must be paid, payment can be made via teller or ATM at the financial institution. Be sure to mention that the payment made is for Zakah. (4) Don't forget to keep proof of payment as proof that Zakah has been paid. (5) After the payment has been successfully made, the financial institution will provide a receipt for the Zakah payment.

Seventh, Zakah from bank interest. In Islam, interest or usury is considered something that is haram and should not be accepted. Therefore, bank interest cannot be considered a halal or pure result. However, if a person has received interest from a bank, then Zakah must be paid on the amount of interest received. The amount of Zakah that must be paid is 2.5% of the amount of interest received. However, it is best for someone not to get or not give bank interest in financial transactions. It's a good idea to look for other alternatives, such as halal investments that do not involve interest, such as investment Zakah, or investing funds in the real sector, such as shares and property.

Eighth, optimize Zakah. Optimizing Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions (LKS) can be done in several ways, including: (1) Increasing the efficiency of Zakah collection and distribution, so that Zakah can be distributed on target and on time; (2) Developing Islamic Financial instruments that enable the collection and utilization of Zakah more effectively and transparently; and (3) Utilizing information technology to simplify the process of collecting, managing and distributing Zakah.

Ninth, take Zakah. The Zakah amil at LKS plays a role in managing the Zakah received from the community. Some of the duties of amil Zakah include: (1) Collecting, managing and distributing Zakah in a good and correct manner in accordance with sharia principles; (2) Providing good service to muzakki and mustahik in the process of collecting and distributing Zakah; and (3) Building and developing a transparent and accountable information system for managing Zakah.

Tenth, Zakah potential. The potential for Zakah in LKS is very large because LKS can become an institution that collects Zakah from the community in an integrated and effective manner. Some of the potential for Zakah in LKS are: (1) LKS can expand the Zakah amil network spread throughout Indonesia so that people can entrust their Zakah to LKS; (2) LKS can utilize information technology to collect and distribute Zakah more effectively and accurately; and (3) LKS can develop Islamic Financial instruments based on Zakah so that people can use their Zakah for investments that are halal and beneficial to society.

Eleventh, Zakah assessment uses Historical Cost and Current Cost. The Historical Cost method refers to the initial value of the asset or the value obtained when the asset was first purchased. In assessing Zakah using the Historical Cost method, the asset value used is the value of the asset when it was purchased or when it was first owned. This method is usually used on fixed assets owned by Islamic financial institutions such as buildings, land and vehicles. The Current Cost method refers to the current market value or the value obtained if the asset is sold today. In assessing Zakah using the Current method Cost, the value of the assets used is the current market value. This method is usually used for liquid assets owned by Islamic financial institutions such as shares, bonds and deposits.

Twelfth, collecting Zakah funds. LKS usually have a Zakah fund collection program as one of the services they offer. This program can be carried out in various ways, such as providing charity boxes at branch offices, offering professional Zakah management services, or holding Zakah collection campaigns. Each LKS may have a different mechanism for collecting and distributing Zakah, but in general they will follow sharia principles in managing Zakah funds.

Thirteenth, the level of Zakah compliance. LKS must ensure that all Zakah funds received and distributed comply with applicable sharia regulations, such as the obligation to pay Zakah and the types of assets that must be Zakahed. LKS must also be able to ensure that the process of collecting, managing and distributing Zakah funds is carried out in a transparent and accountable manner. For this reason, LKS usually relies on sophisticated information technology systems to ensure compliance and transparency in the management of Zakah funds.

Fourteenth, productive Zakah. LKS can help encourage the development of productive Zakah through various programs, such as providing business capital,

educational assistance, or skills training to increase the economic independence of Zakah recipients. In this case, LKS can collaborate with related partners, such as microfinance institutions or educational institutions, to ensure the success of the productive Zakah program.

Fifteenth, Zakah on savings. Savings Zakah is Zakah issued from savings that have reached the nishab (a certain amount) and have been in ownership for one hijriyah year. The amount of Zakah on savings is 2.5% of the total savings owned. Islamic Financial Institutions (LKS) can help their customers to calculate and pay Zakah on savings by taking them directly from the customer's account.

Sixteenth, disclosure of Zakah funds in financial reports. LKS is required to disclose Zakah funds in its financial reports. This aims to provide transparency and accountability regarding the use of Zakah funds collected from the community. Disclosure of Zakah funds in the LKS financial report includes the amount of funds collected, the source of the funds, and the use of the Zakah funds.

Seventeenth, Zakah bank. LKS that wish to transform into a Zakah bank must meet the requirements set by the National Zakah Amil Agency (BAZNAS) and obtain permission from Bank Indonesia. As a Zakah bank, LKS must ensure that the collection of Zakah funds is carried out in a transparent and accountable manner and that the distribution of Zakah funds is carried out to eligible Zakah recipients in a timely manner and in accordance with applicable sharia provisions.

Eighteenth, accounting treatment of Zakah assets. LKS has an obligation to manage and distribute Zakah from its customers in a transparent and accountable manner. Therefore, LKS must take into account the Zakah collected from its customers as part of its financial reports. The Zakah collected must be separated from LKS operational funds and allocated to economic empowerment and social welfare programs for mustahik.

Nineteenth, institutional regulations for Zakah management. Zakah management at LKS is regulated by the National Zakah Amil Agency (BAZNAS) and the Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) in accordance with sharia principles. LKS must be registered and have permission from BAZNAS to collect and distribute Zakah. LKS must also have a Zakah business unit that is separate from its other business units, and have a professional and trained Zakah manager. Zakah managers must follow clear and regular procedures in collecting, calculating and distributing Zakah.

Twentieth, potential Zakah. The potential for Zakah in LKS is very large, considering the large number of customers who use Islamic Financial products and services. LKS can utilize the potential of Zakah to increase economic empowerment and social welfare for mustahik, such as productive economic empowerment programs, educational scholarships and health assistance. By properly utilizing Zakah, LKS can strengthen its position as a financial institution that cares about the social and economic welfare of Muslims.

4.4 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Influence of Zakah

First, financial performance, including: Return On Assets/ROA. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can have a positive impact on financial performance, especially ROA. One way Islamic financial institutions can increase ROA is by allocating Zakah funds to profitable investment instruments. This investment can be in the form of investment in the real sector, such as MSMEs, or investment in financial instruments such as sukuk or shares. Thus, the performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can help increase ROA and the financial health of these institutions.

Second, empowering MSMEs. Zakah can also have a positive impact on empowering MSMEs. Islamic Financial institutions can allocate Zakah funds to MSME empowerment programs, such as training, mentoring or financing. In this

way, MSMEs can improve their business performance and contribute to overall economic growth. Apart from that, empowering MSMEs can also help reduce poverty and social inequality.

Third, the economy. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can also have a positive impact on the economy as a whole. By allocating Zakah funds to real sectors such as MSMEs, Islamic Financial institutions can help increase production, create jobs and increase people's income. This can have a positive impact on economic growth and the overall welfare of society.

Fourth, profitability. Good Zakah performance in Islamic Financial institutions can have a positive impact on profitability. This is because good Zakah performance can increase customer and investor confidence in Islamic Financial institutions. In the long term, this trust can increase the number of customers and investors who choose to transact at Islamic financial institutions, thereby increasing income and profitability. In addition, good Zakah performance can help Islamic Financial institutions optimize fund management and prevent financial risks that could disrupt company performance. Thus, Islamic financial institutions can maintain their profitability consistently.

Fifth, Human Development Index/HDI. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can have a positive impact on HDI. This is because Zakah can help improve the welfare of the people who receive Zakah. Islamic Financial institutions that achieve good Zakah performance can ensure that Zakah funds are distributed effectively and on target to help people in need. In the long term, well-distributed Zakah can help increase people's access to education, health and other basic needs which can increase HDI. As a Islamic Financial institution, good Zakah performance can also strengthen the company's image in the eyes of the public, so that it can attract more customers and investors who choose to make transactions at Islamic Financial institutions.

Sixth, asset investment portfolio. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can have a positive impact on asset investment portfolios. This is because Zakah can help optimize fund management and strengthen the financial position of Islamic Financial institutions, thereby enabling companies to make larger investments and develop wider investment portfolios. In the long term, good Zakah performance can help Islamic financial institutions to diversify their asset investment portfolios and minimize investment risks. In addition, Islamic financial institutions that obtain good Zakah performance can attract more customers and investors who choose to transact with the company, thereby increasing liquidity and strengthening the company's financial position.

Seventh, growth of the non-bank financial industry. Islamic Financial institutions that demonstrate good Zakah performance can help increase public trust in the non-bank financial industry. This can make a significant contribution to the growth of the non-bank financial industry because people tend to look for alternatives to the conventional financial sector which operates on the interest principle.

Eighth, company reputation. Good Zakah performance in Islamic Financial institutions can improve the company's reputation in the eyes of the public. This can have a positive impact on the company's relationships with customers, investors, regulators and society in general. Good Zakah performance shows that the company is committed to contributing to the welfare of society and demonstrating values that are in accordance with sharia principles.

Ninth, company profits. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can have an impact on company profits. In sharia principles, Zakah is a social and spiritual obligation that must be fulfilled by companies. Therefore, companies that can fulfill their Zakah obligations well show that the company operates with strong sharia principles and can have a positive impact on the welfare

of society. In the long term, this can strengthen the company's ties with customers and investors, as well as improve the company's overall financial performance.

Tenth, the number of poor people. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can contribute to increasing the number of poor people being helped. This can happen if Islamic Financial institutions are able to manage Zakah well and effectively, so that the Zakah collected can be distributed on target to people in need. Apart from that, Islamic Financial institutions can also help speed up the process of distributing Zakah by providing financial or non-financial assistance to mustahik (Zakah recipients), such as skills training, education, and so on.

Eleventh, strengthening the Zakah ecosystem. The performance of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions can also influence the strengthening of the Zakah ecosystem. Islamic Financial institutions can act as professional and trusted Zakah managers, so that they can increase public confidence in giving Zakah through Islamic Financial institutions. Apart from that, Islamic Financial institutions can also act as facilitators or coordinators in building cooperation between various parties involved in Zakah management, such as Zakah institutions, the government and the community. This can strengthen the Zakah ecosystem as a whole and increase the effectiveness of Zakah distribution to mustahik.

4.5 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinant Variables of Zakah Performance in Islamic Financial Institutions

First, Intellectual Capital. Intellectual capital can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions because employees and management who have adequate knowledge and skills will be able to manage Zakah funds more effectively and efficiently. By having sufficient intellectual capital, Islamic financial institutions can better identify and manage risks in managing Zakah funds.

Second, employee salaries. Employee salaries also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Employees who receive fair and adequate salaries will feel more motivated and enthusiastic at work. Good salaries can also help attract and retain quality employees, so that Islamic financial institutions can maintain a quality workforce to manage Zakah funds well.

Third, Good Corporate Governance/GCG. GCG can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions because these principles can help build trust between Islamic Financial institutions and the community. By building good trust, people will be more inclined to channel Zakah funds through Islamic Financial institutions, so that Islamic Financial institutions can manage Zakah funds more effectively and efficiently. In addition, by implementing GCG principles, Islamic financial institutions can minimize the risk of fraud and malpractice in managing Zakah funds.

Fourth, liquidity risk. This risk can have an impact on the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions, if the institution cannot fulfill its obligations at the specified time, then this can affect public trust in the institution. In addition, liquidity risk that is too high can hamper the performance of Zakah management because Islamic Financial institutions must fulfill their obligations to pay Zakah at the specified time.

Fifth, financial performance, including: Return On Assets/ROA, Capital Adequacy Ratio/CAR, Financing to Deposit Ratio/FDR, Non Performing Financing/NPF, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO. Financial performance also has a significant influence on the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Good financial performance can enable Islamic Financial institutions to allocate sufficient funds for Zakah management. On the other hand, if financial performance is poor, Islamic financial institutions may have difficulty fulfilling their Zakah payment obligations and this can affect the reputation and public trust in the institution.

Sixth, the size of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS. The size of the Sharia Supervisory Board can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. A large and diverse Sharia Supervisory Board can provide different points of view in determining Zakah management policies. In this case, diversity of opinion can produce better and more effective policies in managing Zakah. In addition, the large size of the Sharia Supervisory Board can provide greater confidence to the public that Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions is carried out in a transparent and professional manner.

Seventh, company size. Company size can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. The larger the company size, the more complex the operations and the amount of Zakah managed. Therefore, larger companies tend to have more complicated management structures and stronger control systems for managing Zakah, which can increase the efficiency and effectiveness of Zakah management.

Eighth, Board of Commissioners. The Board of Commissioners has an important role in supervising the management of Zakah by Islamic Financial institutions. The Board of Commissioners is responsible for ensuring that company management complies with the rules and regulations applicable to Zakah management. Apart from that, the Board of Commissioners must also ensure that Zakah management is carried out transparently, accountably and responsibly.

Ninth, Board of Directors. The Board of Directors has an important role in managing Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions. The Board of Directors is responsible for designing and implementing effective and efficient Zakah management strategies. In addition, the Board of Directors is also responsible for ensuring that the Zakah management system used by the company can produce accurate and reliable reports.

Tenth, capital risk. Capital risk can affect the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions because low capital can hinder the institution's ability to carry out optimal activities in collecting and distributing Zakah. On the other hand, strong capital can help institutions expand their reach and improve their operational performance.

Eleventh, inflation rate. The inflation rate can also affect the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. An increase in inflation can increase institutional operational costs, thereby reducing the efficiency of Zakah management. Apart from that, inflation can also affect the value of Zakah collected and distributed, so that it can affect the effectiveness of the use of Zakah funds.

Twelfth, profitability ratio. The profitability ratio can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions because institutions that have a high level of profitability can have a greater ability to collect and distribute Zakah. However, it is important to remember that the main aim of managing Zakah is not to make a profit, but to fulfill religious obligations and help people in need.

Thirteenth, Community Development Based according to Ibnu Khaldun. This concept can help improve the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. This approach emphasizes the importance of community participation in Zakah management, so that it can strengthen program sustainability and increase the effectiveness of Zakah distribution. Apart from that, this approach can also help increase community involvement in strengthening social networks, so that it can improve the economic and social conditions of communities in need.

4.6 Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Determinant Variables of Zakah in Islamic Financial Institutions

First, personal factors, including: age, stage of life, job, economic situation, personality, self-concept, lifestyle. Age can influence the performance of Zakah

management in Islamic Financial institutions. Older managers may have broader experience in managing Zakah, but may be less familiar with new technology and changes in financial regulations. Younger managers may be more adept at using technology and familiar with regulatory changes, but may be less experienced in managing Zakah. Life stages can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Managers just starting out in their careers may focus more on learning and skill development, while older managers may focus more on experience and leading a team. Work can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Managers working in Islamic financial institutions may have more specific experience and knowledge of Islamic financial regulations and processes, while managers from non-financial backgrounds may be more adept in terms of general management and leadership. Economic conditions can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. When the economy is difficult, people may have difficulty giving Zakah, and Islamic financial institutions may have fewer funds to manage. On the other hand, when the economy is good, people may be more able to give Zakah, and Islamic financial institutions may have more funds to manage. Personality can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Managers who have strong, confident personalities may find it easier to lead teams and make difficult decisions, while managers who are more introverted may be more inclined to work alone. Self-concept can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Managers who have a positive self-concept and are confident in their abilities may be more successful in managing Zakah and leading teams, while managers who lack self-confidence may be less successful. A person's lifestyle can influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. For example, if someone has an extravagant lifestyle and does not pay attention to good financial management, then he may not be able to manage Zakah well. On the other hand, if someone has a frugal lifestyle and is disciplined in financial management, then he may be more inclined to manage Zakah well.

Second, psychological factors, including: motivation, perception, learning, memory. A person's motivation can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Someone who has high motivation to manage Zakah well, for example, because they want to get a reward or help people in need, will be more likely to manage Zakah well. A person's perception of the importance of Zakah can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. If someone has a good perception of the importance of Zakah and its positive impact on society, then he or she may be more inclined to manage Zakah well. A person's ability to learn and understand Islamic Financial concepts and Zakah management can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Someone who has good learning skills and understands these concepts will be better able to manage Zakah well. A person's ability to remember information and details about Zakah can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. Someone who has good memory skills will find it easier to manage Zakah well and avoid mistakes that might occur.

Third, the attitude of donors. The attitude of donors greatly influences the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. If donors have a positive attitude towards Zakah management, they will be more inclined to give their Zakah to Islamic Financial institutions that have a good reputation in Zakah management. In this case, Islamic financial institutions will receive more Zakah funds which can be used to help people in need. On the other hand, if donors feel distrustful or uncertain about the management of Zakah in Islamic Financial institutions, they may not give their Zakah to that institution.

Fourth, cultural factors, including: culture, subculture, social class. Culture and subculture can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. For example, in a culture that values social involvement and service, Islamic financial institutions that are active in social activities and have programs that help people in need can be more trusted and respected. On the other hand, if in certain subcultures, Zakah is considered more of an individual responsibility and not a community responsibility, then Islamic financial institutions may have difficulty collecting Zakah funds from the community. Social class can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. People with higher social classes may have different perceptions about Zakah and how it is managed. For example, they may be more interested in economic and business development programs supported by Zakah. On the other hand, people with lower social classes may be more in need of direct assistance and transparent and effective Zakah management to meet their basic needs.

Fifth, social factors, including: reference group, family, role and status. In the context of Zakah management in Islamic financial institutions, reference groups can influence Zakah management performance through their influence on norms, values and individual behavior in the organization. If the reference group within the organization has positive values and norms regarding Zakah management, then the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions can increase. Families can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions through the values and norms they teach to family members who work in the organization. Families that have positive values and norms regarding Zakah management can form individuals who are highly committed to social and financial responsibility in Zakah management. The role and status of individuals within the organization can also influence the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions. If individuals have an important role in the organization, then they will have greater responsibility in managing Zakah. Status can also influence individual behavior in managing Zakah, for example individuals with high status tend to be more committed to showing good performance in their work.

Sixth, subjective norms. In the context of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions, subjective norms can influence Zakah management performance through individual views regarding their social and financial responsibilities in Zakah management. If the subjective norms held by individuals within the organization regarding Zakah management are positive, then the performance of Zakah management in Islamic Financial institutions can increase.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- Number of research publications around Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions during the period 2013 to 2022, shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 60 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is an economics journal, with 11 articles.
- The most productive researcher in publishing research results is Rika Febri Ramdhani (Tadulako University, Palu) who wrote 2 journal articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Zakah Management in Islamic Financial Institutions are divided into 11 clusters and 133 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 21 topics, cluster 2 consists of 21 topics, cluster 3 consists of 16 topics, cluster 4 consists of 14 topics, cluster 5 consists of 12 topics, and cluster 6 consists of 11 topics,

cluster 7 consists of 10 topics, cluster 8 consists of 10 topics, cluster 9 consists of 8 topics, cluster 10 consists of 6 topics, and cluster 11 consists of 4 topics.

- Based on the Library Research, there are 3 main research themes, namely: (1) Zakah management; (2) The influence caused; and (3) Determinant variables of Zakah performance; and (4) The determinant variable of Zakah.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the Library Research study can be explained in a more complex way.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Library Research Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY

RESEARCH. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>

- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Library Research. *Syiar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Library Research. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Bank Bukopin Syariah dan

- Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LIBRARY RESEARCH. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Library Research. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>